

Supporting Information:

Polymer-assisted Crystallization and Defect Passivation in Planar Wide Bandgap FAPbBr₃ Perovskite Solar Cells

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Figure S1: (a) UV–Vis absorbance spectra of FAPbBr₃ films with and without PMMA treatment and (b, c) Tauc plots used to estimate the optical bandgap (E_g), showing $E_g \approx 2.28$ eV for both samples.

Figure S2: Extraction of Urbach energy (E_u) from PDS spectra for (a) untreated and (b) PMMA-treated FAPbBr₃ films, demonstrating reduced energetic disorder upon PMMA incorporation.

The carrier lifetime is obtained by fitting the PL transient decays with a bi-exponential decay function as follows

$$f(t) = A_1 \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\tau_1}\right) + A_2 \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\tau_2}\right) + B$$

where A_1 and A_2 represent the time-independent decay amplitudes, B is a constant, and τ_1 and τ_2 are the fast and slow decay time, respectively. The weighted-average lifetime (τ_{avg}) is calculated from the fit curve parameters according to the following equation.

$$\tau_{avg} = \frac{A_1 \tau_1^2 + A_2 \tau_2^2}{A_1 \tau_1 + A_2 \tau_2}$$

Table S1. Summary of the fit and calculated parameters of the TRPL spectra of the FAPbBr₃ perovskite films prepared without and with PMMA anti-solvent treatment.

Sample name	A ₁ (%)	τ ₁ (ns)	A ₂ (%)	τ ₂ (ns)	Average τ (ns)
FAPbBr ₃	83.40	5.88	16.60	41.95	27.05
FAPbBr ₃ -PMMA	77.40	8.30	22.60	51.07	35.78

Figure S3: Space-charge-limited current (SCLC) measurements of electron-only devices fabricated with (a) untreated and (b) PMMA-treated FAPbBr₃ films, showing trap-filled limit voltages (V_{TFL}) and calculated trap densities (N_t).

Figure S4: The external quantum efficiency (EQE) spectra and integrated J_{sc} for the best performing the FAPbBr₃ perovskite solar cells prepared without and with PMMA anti-solvent treatment.

Figure S5: Statistical distribution box plots of (a)Voc, (b) Jsc and (c)FF for the FAPbBr₃ perovskite solar cells prepared without and with PMMA anti-solvent treatment.

Table S2: Summary of the average photovoltaic parameters of the FAPbBr₃ perovskite solar cells prepared without and with PMMA anti-solvent treatment.

Name	Voc (V)	Jsc(mA/cm ²)	FF(%)	PCE(%)
FAPbBr ₃	1.354 ± 0.040	7.60 ± 0.21	48.1 ± 4.4	4.95 ± 0.55
FAPbBr ₃ -PMMA	1.468 ± 0.028	7.63 ± 0.23	55.1 ± 3.1	6.16 ± 0.31

Figure S6: Current density-voltage (J-V) curves under reverse and forward scans the FAPbBr₃ perovskite solar cells prepared without and with PMMA anti-solvent treatment.

Table S3: Summary of the photovoltaic parameters of reverse and forward scans for the best performing FAPbBr₃ perovskite solar cells prepared without and with PMMA anti-solvent treatment.

Name	Voc (V)	Jsc (mA/cm²)	FF (%)	PCE(%)	H-Index (%)
FAPbBr ₃ :Reverse	1.395	7.79	51.3	5.57	13.8 %
FAPbBr ₃ :Forward	1.302	7.59	48.6	4.80	
FAPbBr ₃ -PMMA: Reverse	1.510	7.75	55.4	6.48	5.1 %
FAPbBr ₃ -PMMA: Forward	1.486	7.71	53.7	6.15	

Table S4: Summary of the photovoltaic parameters of initial and after 4 weeks stored under ambient conditions for the FAPbBr₃ perovskite solar cells prepared without and with PMMA anti-solvent treatment.

Name	Voc (V)	Jsc (mA/cm ²)	FF (%)	PCE(%)	PCE-Retention(%)
FAPbBr ₃ :Initial	1.395	7.79	51.3	5.57	
FAPbBr ₃ : After 4 weeks	1.311	7.01	47.2	4.34	77.9 %
FAPbBr ₃ -PMMA: Initial	1.510	7.75	55.4	6.48	
FAPbBr ₃ -PMMA: After 4 weeks	1.463	7.43	54.4	5.91	91.2 %

Table S5: Comparison of key performance metrics for high-performing FAPbBr₃ perovskite solar cells reported in the literature.

Device structure	Voc(V)	Jsc (mA/cm ²)	FF (%)	PCE (%)	Method	Ref
FTO/TiO ₂ /FAPbBr ₃ / Spiro-OMeTAD/Au	1.35	6.6	73	6.5	Two- step	[1]
FTO/ compact TiO ₂ /Li treated mesoporous TiO ₂ / FAPbBr ₃ /spiro-OMeTAD/ Au	1.53	7.3	71	8.2	Two -step	[2]
FTO/d-TiO ₂ /FAPbBr ₃ /spiro-OMeTAD/Au	1.32	6.3	69	5.7	Single step	[3]
FTO/Compact TiO ₂ /meso TiO ₂ /FAPbBr ₃ / HTL (Fluorene–Dithiophene) /Au	1.5	6.9	69	7.1	Two- step	[4]
FTO/PEDOT: PSS/FAPbBr ₃ (HBr)/PCBM/Zno	1.35	10.3	59	8.3	Single step	[5]
FTO/SnO ₂ /FAPbBr ₃ (Urea)/ spiro-OMeTAD /Au	1.56	8.39	73	10.61	Two -step	[6]
FTO/TiO ₂ /Cs _{0.08} FA _{0.92} PbBr ₃ /PTTA/Au	1.515	6.6	83.2	8.32	Two- step	[7]
FTO/SnO ₂ /FAPbBr ₃ / PEABr/SpiroOMeTAD/Au	1.39	8.8	77.6	9.4	Two- steps	[8]
FTO/NiO/FAPbBr ₃ /Mg-ZnO/PCBM/BCP/Ag	1.44	8.92	71	9.06	Single step	[9]
FTO/TiO ₂ /Li-m- TiO ₂ /FAPbBr ₃ /PMMA/spiro/Au	1.53	6.96	74	7.8	Two- steps	[10]
ITO/P3CT/FAPbBr ₃ /TET/PCBM/C60/BCP/Cu	1.482	8.50	66.52	8.33	Two step	[11]
ITO/MoO _x /P3CT/FAPbBr ₃ (CsAc)/BCP/ /(AZO/C ₆₀ / BCP)/Au	1.404	8.00	62.60	7.03	Two- step	[12]
ITO/SnO ₂ /FAPbBr ₃ (GABr)/Spiro-OMeTAD/Au	1.639	7.71	71	8.92	Single step	[13]
FTO/PEDOT:PSS/FAPbBr ₃ (MACl)/Spiro-OMeTAD/Au	1.38	8.6	78.04	9.26	Two -step	[14]
FTO/SnO ₂ /FAPbBr ₃ (MACl)/carbon	1.571	8.35	82.8	10.86	Single step	[15]
ITO/NiO _x /2PACz)/ FAPbBr ₃ /C60/BCP/Ag	1.45	8.62	69.72	8.71	Single step	[16]
ITO/NiO _x /PTTA / FAPbBr ₃ /C60/BCP/Ag	1.43	8.63	61.25	7.52	Single step	[16]
FTO/ NiO _x /2PACz/ perovskite/ Cl-TPPO/C ₆₀ /BCP/Ag	1.41	8.92	77.3	9.73	Single step	[17]
FTO/ NiO _x /1-2PACz/ perovskite/ Cl-TPPO/C ₆₀ /BCP/Ag	1.51	9.16	80.6	11.4	Single step	[17]
FTO/TiO ₂ /SnO ₂ /FAPbBr ₃ (BMIMBF ₄)/ ISO-ENO/PTTA/ITO	1.64	6.69	70.03	7.83	Single step	[18]
ITO/SnO ₂ /FAPbBr ₃ (PMMA)/ Spiro-OMeTAD/Au	1.510	7.75	55.4	6.48	Single step	This work

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